

INNOVATIVE AIRBORNE WATER LEAK DETECTION SURVEILLANCE SERVICE

The WADI project will prove the feasibility of an airborne water leak detection surveillance service aimed at providing water utilities with adequate information on leaks in water infrastructure outside urban areas, thus enabling prompt and cost-effective repairs.

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EFFICIENCY

WADI leak detection service will help saving water, consequently reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions.

EFFECTIVENESS

Long distance and strategic infrastructure monitoring also in areas with difficult physical access.

ADAPTABILITY

Accurate and tailored leak detection method for water transportation infrastructure (irrigation and pipe water network).

IMPACT ON THE ENVIRONMENT

By reducing losses from water supply systems WADI's service will contribute to tackling water scarcity and drought.

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REAL ENVIRONMENT DEMONSTRATION

WADI Technology will be tested in the field.

Technology

- Optical remote sensing
- Manned and unmanned aerial platforms
- Demonstration in operational environment

WADI's innovative concept consists in coupling and optimising off-the-shelf optical remote sensing devices (multispectral and infrared cameras) and applying them on two complementary aerial platforms (manned and unmanned) in an operational environment.

The feasibility of the airborne surveillance service will be tested through leak detection campaigns on two pilot sites: Société du Canal de Provence (Provence region, France) and EDIA (Alqueva, Portugal).

The WADI project is coordinated by youris.com EEIG. Scientific coordination is provided by Onera. The project involves 12 partners in 6 European countries:

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